

Atlantic Manatí, August 30, 2025

Mr.

Fernando Antonio Oliveros Ocampo (Academic coordinator).

Receive a warm and respectful greeting,

This is to kindly request your authorization to conduct an academic research at the Maruja del Rosario Aguilar Educational Institution in Manatí, Atlántico, in the field of mathematics education, which is titled: **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS**, in the company of other researchers who are experts in the subject matter to contribute to the students' learning.

The main objective of this study is to detect the mathematical connections that emerge when students construct conceptions of slope through interaction with the PhET Colorado simulator Graphing Lines. Therefore, your child will participate through virtual interaction with the simulator to enhance and characterize their mathematical knowledge. For this purpose, we require from you a select group of students from the 8th-9th validation cycle, since the topic concerning the line is mostly covered in these grades. On the other hand, we kindly request the possibility that the institution provides its facilities and resources to work with the simulator effectively.

We are committed to complying with all rules and regulations established by the institution, as well as respecting the designated schedules and spaces. Likewise, we emphasize that we are open to your recommendations and suggestions regarding the implementation of the instructional sequence. For this purpose, students who are candidates for selection must have informed consent from their parents to avoid any inconveniences. All data, photographs, and previously collected information will be used exclusively for academic purposes, ensuring confidentiality.

For any inquiries, the following email addresses are available: rrolivero@mail.uniatlantico.edu.co and elenaprodriguez@mail.uniatlantico.edu.co, as well as the cellphone numbers attached below. We are available for any meeting or interview you deem necessary to discuss our request in more detail and answer any questions that may arise.

We thank you in advance for your attention and consideration of our request, as well as your valuable support for the project.

Sincerely,

Ronaldo Rafael Olivero-Acuña
Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics
University of the Atlantic
Cellphone number: 3017012963

Recibido
Fernando Oliveros
30/Agosto/2025

Elena Patricia Rodríguez-Carrillo
Student: Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics
University of Atlantic
Cell phone number: 3107237957

Atlantic Manatí, September 3, 2025

Mr./Mrs.

Parent and/or guardian

Receive a warm and respectful greeting,

We are writing to you in order to request your kind authorization to conduct the research entitled: **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS**, where the student *Karelys Marquez Caigua* (S1), who is under your supervision, was considered as a potential participant.

The main objective of this study is to detect the mathematical connections that emerge when students construct conceptions of slope through interaction with the PhET Colorado simulator Graphing Lines. Therefore, your child will participate through virtual interaction with the simulator to enhance and characterize their mathematical knowledge. To carry out this research, it is essential to have your consent and/or approval.

We are committed to complying with all rules and regulations established by the institution, as well as respecting the designated schedules and spaces. In addition, any data or information collected will be used exclusively for academic purposes, and its confidentiality will be ensured.

For any inquiries, the following email addresses are available: rrolivero@mail.uniatlantico.edu.co and elenaprodriguez@mail.uniatlantico.edu.co, as well as the cellphone numbers attached below. We are available for any meeting or interview you deem necessary to discuss our request in more detail and answer any questions that may arise.

We thank you in advance for your attention and consideration of our request, as well as your valuable support for the project. To authorize your child's participation, we ask that you complete and sign the attached form and send it back to the school.

Sincerely,

Ronaldo Rafael Olivero Acuña
Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics
University of the Atlantic
Cellphone number: 3017012963

Elena Patricia Rodríguez Carrillo
Student: Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics
University of Atlantic
Cell phone number: 3107237957

Atlantic Manatí, September 3, 2025

Mr./Mrs.

Parent and/or guardian

Receive a warm and respectful greeting,

We are writing to you in order to request your kind authorization to conduct the research entitled: **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS**, where the student *Dorlan Santana Amorteguis (S2)*, who is under your supervision, was considered as a potential participant.

The main objective of this study is to detect the mathematical connections that emerge when students construct conceptions of slope through interaction with the PhET Colorado simulator Graphing Lines. Therefore, your child will participate through virtual interaction with the simulator to enhance and characterize their mathematical knowledge. To carry out this research, it is essential to have your consent and/or approval.

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Sincerely,

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University of the Atlantic
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Elena Patricia Rodríguez Carrillo
Student: Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics
University of Atlantic
Cell phone number: 3107237957

Atlantic Manatí, September 3, 2025

Mr./Mrs.

Parent and/or guardian

Receive a warm and respectful greeting,

We are writing to you in order to request your kind authorization to conduct the research entitled: **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS**, where the student *Daniela Guerrero Araujo* (S3), who is under your supervision, was considered as a potential participant.

The main objective of this study is to detect the mathematical connections that emerge when students construct conceptions of slope through interaction with the PhET Colorado simulator Graphing Lines. Therefore, your child will participate through virtual interaction with the simulator to enhance and characterize their mathematical knowledge. To carry out this research, it is essential to have your consent and/or approval.

We are committed to complying with all rules and regulations established by the institution, as well as respecting the designated schedules and spaces. In addition, any data or information collected will be used exclusively for academic purposes, and its confidentiality will be ensured.

For any inquiries, the following email addresses are available: rrolivero@mail.uniatlantico.edu.co and elenaprodiguez@mail.uniatlantico.edu.co, as well as the cellphone numbers attached below. We are available for any meeting or interview you deem necessary to discuss our request in more detail and answer any questions that may arise.

We thank you in advance for your attention and consideration of our request, as well as your valuable support for the project. To authorize your child's participation, we ask that you complete and sign the attached form and send it back to the school.

Sincerely,

Ronaldo Rafael Olivero-Acuña
Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics
University of the Atlantic
Cell phone number: 3017012963

Elena Patricia Rodríguez-Carrillo
Student: Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics
University of Atlantic
Cell phone number: 3107237957

Informed Consent Form (S1)

I, *Abimael Mosquera Machacón*, have been informed about the research entitled **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS**, and I authorize the voluntary participation of my child *Karelys Marquez Caigua* in this project.

Signature of Parent or Guardian:

Informed Consent Form (S2)

I, *Lizyenis Amorteguis Carrillo*, have been informed about the research entitled **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS**, and I authorize the voluntary participation of my child *Dorlan Santana Amorteguis* in this project.

Signature of Parent or Guardian:

Informed Consent Form (S3)

I, *Jonatan Guzmán Guerrero Coronado*, have been informed about the research entitled **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS**, and I authorize the voluntary participation of my child *Daniela Guerrero Araujo* in this project.

Signature of Parent or Guardian:

**INSTITUCION EDUCATIVA MARUJA DEL ROSARIO AGUILAR
DE MANATI ATLANTICO**

APROBADA POR LA SECRETARIA DE EDUCACION DEL
DEPARTAMENTO DEL ATLANTICO
Según Resolución N°. 1195 de 30 de abril de 2024

Dirección Calle 4 # 4 – 30 Manatí – Atlántico, barrio emisora.
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Matricula Mercantil: 00.00020928
Email: wual_09@hotmail.com Celular: 3216803975

**THE UNDERSIGNED ACADEMIC COORDINATOR OF THE MARUJA DEL ROSARIO AGUILAR
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION OF MANATI ATLANTICO**

CERTIFIES

Researchers **RONALDO RAFAEL OLIVERO-ACUÑA** and **ELENA PATRICIA RODRÍGUEZ-CARRILLO** successfully developed the implementation of the instructional sequence of the research titled: **USE OF THE PHET COLORADO 'GRAPHING LINES' SIMULATOR TO BUILD CONCEPTUALIZATIONS OF SLOPE: A VIEW FROM MATHEMATICAL CONNECTIONS** through a case study with three (3) students of the Integrated Special Academic Cycles 4 (CLEI 4), grades 8th-9th of this educational institution, complying with institutional guidelines and contributing to the strengthening of pedagogical processes in the area of Mathematics through technology.

This certification is issued to the interested party on the 15th day of September 2025.

Fernando Oliveros

ENG. FERNANDO OLIVEROS OCAMPO

ACADEMIC COORDINATOR.

C.C. No. 1.001.865.500 Manati

Cell phone number 3058290062